

Sonata

per il Cimbalo, Flauto traverso e Violino

Zach, Jan

Lento

Flöte

Violine

Cembalo

6

10

*) Siehe kritischer Bericht

15 **Vivace**

Musical score for measures 15-18. The score is in 2/4 time with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). It features two systems of staves. The first system has two treble clef staves. The second system has a grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The music includes triplets and various rhythmic patterns. The tempo is marked 'Vivace'.

19

Musical score for measures 19-22. The score is in 2/4 time with a key signature of three sharps. It features two systems of staves. The first system has two treble clef staves. The second system has a grand staff. The music includes triplets, trills (tr), and various rhythmic patterns. The tempo is marked 'Vivace'.

23

Musical score for measures 23-26. The score is in 2/4 time with a key signature of three sharps. It features two systems of staves. The first system has two treble clef staves. The second system has a grand staff. The music includes triplets and various rhythmic patterns. The tempo is marked 'Vivace'.

28

Musical score for measures 28-33. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Measure 28 features a melodic line in the treble clef and a bass line in the bass clef. A trill (tr) is marked above the first note of measure 29. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of measure 33.

34

Musical score for measures 34-38. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Measure 34 features a melodic line in the treble clef and a bass line in the bass clef. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of measure 38.

39

Musical score for measures 39-43. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Measure 39 features a melodic line in the treble clef and a bass line in the bass clef. A trill (tr) is marked above the first note of measure 39. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of measure 43.

*) Im Original a

43

Musical score for measures 43-48. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). It features a piano accompaniment with a triplet in measure 45 and trills in measures 43, 44, 46, and 47.

49

Musical score for measures 49-53. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). It features a piano accompaniment with trills in measures 49, 50, 51, and 52, and a first ending bracket in measure 49.

54

Musical score for measures 54-58. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). It features a piano accompaniment with trills in measures 54, 55, and 56, and a second ending bracket in measure 54.

*1) Im Original gis

*2) Im Original fis

60

Musical score for measures 60-65. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with eighth and sixteenth notes, including triplets in measures 60, 64, and 65. The piano accompaniment consists of chords and moving lines in both hands.

66

Musical score for measures 66-71. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The music continues with eighth and sixteenth notes, featuring triplets in measures 66, 67, 70, and 71. The piano accompaniment includes chords and moving lines in both hands.

72

Musical score for measures 72-77. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The music continues with eighth and sixteenth notes, featuring a triplet in measure 72 and a note marked with an asterisk (*) in measure 74. The piano accompaniment includes chords and moving lines in both hands.

*) Im Original a

78

Musical score for measures 78-82. The score is in 3/4 time and consists of three systems. The first system contains measures 78-80, the second system contains measures 81-82. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The first system features a complex melodic line in the upper voice with many sixteenth notes and a descending eighth-note line in the lower voice. The second system shows a melodic line in the upper voice with a long slur over measures 81 and 82, and a more active bass line.

83

Musical score for measures 83-87. The score is in 3/4 time and consists of three systems. The first system contains measures 83-85, the second system contains measures 86-87. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The first system features a complex melodic line in the upper voice with many sixteenth notes and a descending eighth-note line in the lower voice. The second system shows a melodic line in the upper voice with a long slur over measures 86 and 87, and a more active bass line.

88

Musical score for measures 88-92. The score is in 3/4 time and consists of three systems. The first system contains measures 88-90, the second system contains measures 91-92. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The first system features a melodic line in the upper voice with a long slur over measures 88 and 89, and a more active bass line. The second system shows a melodic line in the upper voice with a long slur over measures 91 and 92, and a more active bass line. The score includes trills (tr) in the upper voice.

*) Im Original (Violine)

Polonese

Andante

Flöte

Violine

Andante

Cembalo

5

10

15

Musical score for measures 15-19. The score is in G major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. It consists of three systems of staves. The first system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a piano accompaniment. The second system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The third system has a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The music features a repeating melodic motif in the treble clef and a rhythmic accompaniment in the grand staff.

20

Musical score for measures 20-23. The score is in G major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. It consists of three systems of staves. The first system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a piano accompaniment. The second system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The third system has a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The music continues the melodic motif from the previous system, with some variations in the piano accompaniment.

24

Musical score for measures 24-27. The score is in G major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. It consists of three systems of staves. The first system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a piano accompaniment. The second system has a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The third system has a grand staff with piano accompaniment. The music concludes the melodic motif and features a final piano accompaniment.

28

Musical score for measures 28-32. The score is written for two vocal staves (Soprano and Alto) and a piano accompaniment. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 7/8. The vocal parts feature melodic lines with slurs and accents. The piano accompaniment consists of chords and rhythmic patterns in both hands.

33

Musical score for measures 33-35. The score is written for two vocal staves (Soprano and Alto) and a piano accompaniment. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 7/8. The vocal parts continue with melodic lines. The piano accompaniment features a steady eighth-note bass line and chordal accompaniment in the right hand.

36

Musical score for measures 36-38. The score is written for two vocal staves (Soprano and Alto) and a piano accompaniment. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 7/8. The vocal parts conclude with sustained notes. The piano accompaniment ends with a final chord and a whole note in the bass.

Tempo di Minuet

Flöte

Violine

Cembalo

9

17

*) Im Original h

24 Fine 11

tr 3 3 tr Fine

tr 3 tr Fine

3 3 tr tr Fine

Minore

Flöte

Violine

Cembalo

6

3 tr 3 3

11 Da Capo al Fine

3 3 tr

Kritischer Bericht

Sonate per il Cimbalo, Flauto traverso e Violino (ZACH JAN)

LENTO

Takt 2 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 4 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 9 (Violine)	Ais als Wechselnote des Trillers, da in Takt 8 ebenso Ais vorkommt
Takt 11 (Flöte)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 14 (Cembalo)	Langer Vorschlag
Takt 37 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 39 (Flöte)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 41 (Flöte)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 42 (Violine)	Im Original a, aufgrund des Harmonischen Zusammenhangs geändert auf h
Takt 48	Langer Vorschlag bei allen Stimmen
Takt 49/51 (Flöte)	Im Original gis, aufgrund des Harmonischen Zusammenhangs geändert auf g
Takt 53 (Flöte)	Langer Vorschlag
Takt 56 (Flöte)	Im Original fis, aufgrund des Taktes 54 aufgelöst auf f
Takt 64 (Flöte)	Langer Vorschlag
Takt 72 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 75 (Violine)	Im Original a, aufgrund des Stimmverlaufs abgeändert auf h
Takt 84 (Cembalo)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 89 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 92 (Violine, Flöte)	Notenwert angepasst an das Cembalo

POLONESE

Takt 1 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebögen ergänzt
Takt 2 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 3 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 3 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 4 (Cembalo)	Kurzer Vorschlag
Takt 17/18 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 18/19 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 18/19 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 26 (Flöte)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 27 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 27 (Flöte)	Im Original fis, aufgrund des Harmonischen Zusammenhangs geändert auf g
Takt 29 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 29/30 (Cembalo)	Vorschläge ergänzt
Takt 31 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 33 (Flöte, Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 38 (Violine)	Bindebogen ergänzt
Takt 38 (Cembalo)	Langer Vorschlag

TEMPO DI MINUET

Takt 12 (Flöte, Violine)	Notenwerte auf Viertel und Achtel geändert
Takt 16 (Flöte)	Im Original h, aufgrund des Harmonischen Zusammenhangs geändert auf cis
Takt 22 (Flöte, Violine)	Notenwerte auf Viertel und Achtel geändert
Takt 30 (Violine)	Vorschlag weggelassen
Takt 30 (Flöte, Violine)	Notenwerte angeglichen